

Supplementary Material

A Systematic Literature Review of Incident Response Management Maturity Models

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SM-A. Complete Search Strings

- **Scopus:** (TITLE(("cybersecurity" OR "cyber security" OR "information security" OR "IT security") AND (incident* AND (management OR response OR handling OR "life cycle"))) AND ("maturity model" OR "maturity assessment" OR "maturity framework" OR "capability model" OR "process maturity" OR "readiness" OR "preparedness")) OR ABS(("cybersecurity" OR "cyber security" OR "information security" OR "IT security") AND (incident* AND (management OR response OR handling OR "life cycle"))) AND ("maturity model" OR "maturity assessment" OR "maturity framework" OR "capability model" OR "process maturity" OR "readiness" OR "preparedness")) OR AUTHKEY(("cybersecurity" OR "cyber security" OR "information security" OR "IT security") AND (incident* AND (management OR response OR handling OR "life cycle"))) AND ("maturity model" OR "maturity assessment" OR "maturity framework" OR "capability model" OR "process maturity" OR "readiness" OR "preparedness"))
- **WoS:** ((TI=("cybersecurity" OR "cyber security" OR "information security" OR "IT security") AND TI=(incident* AND (management OR response OR handling OR "life cycle"))) AND TI=("maturity model" OR "maturity assessment" OR "maturity framework" OR "capability model" OR "process maturity" OR "readiness" OR "preparedness")) OR (AB=("cybersecurity" OR "cyber security" OR "information security" OR "IT security") AND AB=(incident* AND (management OR response OR handling OR "life cycle"))) AND AB=("maturity model" OR "maturity assessment" OR "maturity framework" OR "capability model" OR "process maturity" OR "readiness" OR "preparedness")) OR (AK=("cybersecurity" OR "cyber security" OR "information security" OR "IT security") AND AK=(incident* AND (management OR response OR handling OR "life cycle"))) AND AK=("maturity model" OR "maturity assessment" OR "maturity framework" OR "capability model" OR "process maturity" OR "readiness" OR "preparedness")))

This search strategy was designed to maximize coverage of relevant IRM MMs while minimizing the inclusion of unrelated cybersecurity literature.

SM-B. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Table 1 summarizes the inclusion and exclusion criteria applied in this SLR.

Table 1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria for the systematic review

Criterion	Inclusion	Exclusion
Type of study	I1: Primary studies proposing, extending, or empirically applying IRM maturity models	E1: Secondary studies (systematic literature reviews, mappings, surveys, or meta-analyses without primary evidence)
Accessibility	I2: Full-text articles available	E2: Studies not accessible in full text
Relevance to the topic	I3: Studies explicitly focused on IRM MMs	E3: Studies not focused on IRM MMs
Type of publication	I4: Peer-reviewed primary studies published in scientific journals or international conference proceedings	E4: Grey literature and non-peer-reviewed sources (technical reports, white papers, blogs, posters, editorials, and workshop papers without full peer review)
Extension / detail	I5: Studies providing sufficient methodological, conceptual, or empirical detail to enable structured comparison	E5: Short papers (<5 pages) or formats such as posters, editorials, extended abstracts, or technical notes lacking substantive content
Duplication / update	I6: Unique studies or the most complete and recent published version	E6: Duplicate publications or preliminary versions superseded by later publications
Period	I7: Publications between 2000 and 2025	E7: Publications outside the defined time range
Language	I8: Articles written in English	E8: Articles written in other languages

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Table 1 – continued

Criterion	Inclusion	Exclusion
Keywords	I9: Studies including terms related to cybersecurity, incident response/management, and maturity models in the title, keywords, or abstract	E9: Studies that do not include such terms in the title, keywords, or abstract

Secondary studies were excluded to avoid overlap with existing reviews and to focus the analysis on primary evidence underlying IRM maturity model proposals.

SM-C. Quality Assessment Results

The responses to the QA questions were evaluated using a three-level scoring scheme, as presented in Table 2. Each QA question will receive a score based on the completeness and clarity of the information provided:

- **1.0 (Yes):** The aspect evaluated by the QA question is explicitly addressed in the study, providing a complete and clearly understandable explanation.
- **0.5 (Partially):** The aspect is partially addressed, either implicitly or with incomplete information, but sufficient to allow partial evaluation.
- **0.0 (No):** The aspect is not addressed in the study, or there is insufficient information to infer it.

This scoring scheme ensures a consistent and transparent evaluation of academic studies proposing, extending, or analyzing maturity, readiness, or capability models for incident response management.

The maximum attainable score in the quality assessment (QA) is 6.0, corresponding to the total of 6 evaluation questions used in this stage, while the minimum score is 0.0. The maximum total score can be expressed as follows:

$$\text{Maximum score} = 6 \times 1 = 6 \quad (1)$$

A minimum QA score of 4.2 was established as the threshold for including a study in the systematic literature review (SLR). The percentage of criteria satisfied by this threshold is calculated as:

$$\text{Percentage of criteria met} = \frac{\text{Minimum score required}}{\text{Maximum score}} \times 100 = \frac{4.2}{6} \times 100 = 70\% \quad (2)$$

Table 2: Quality assessment scoring scheme for academic studies

Category	Description	Score
Yes	The aspect evaluated by the QA question is explicitly addressed in the study, providing a complete and clearly understandable explanation of the model’s dimensions, levels, evaluation methods, or applicability.	1.0
Partially	The aspect is partially addressed, either implicitly or with incomplete information, allowing only a partial evaluation.	0.5
No	The aspect is not addressed in the study, or there is insufficient information to infer it.	0.0

Setting a 70% threshold ensures the inclusion of methodologically rigorous, conceptually clear, and relevant studies, enabling the detailed review stage to focus on academically robust contributions; this cutoff is widely adopted in systematic literature reviews within software engineering and cybersecurity as an effective balance between rigor and inclusiveness, avoiding premature exclusion of relevant work while maintaining acceptable quality standards [Kitchenham and Charters, 2007].

Table 3: Selected documents and quality assessment results, sorted by reference and publication year

Ref.	Title	Venue	Country	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Score
[Wahlgren et al., 2016]	IT Security incidents escalation in the Swedish financial sector: A maturity model study	Conference Proceedings	Sweden	1	1	1	1	1	1	6.0
[Rieger and Tjoa, 2019]	A Readiness Model for Measuring the Maturity of Cyber Security Incident Management	Conference Proceedings	Austria	1	1	0.5	1	1	0.5	5.0
[Wahlgren and Kowalski, 2019]	A Maturity Model for IT-Related Security Incident Management	Conference Proceedings	Sweden	1	0.5	0.5	1	1	0.5	4.5
[Schlette et al., 2021]	CTI-SOC2M2 – The Quest for Mature, Intelligence-Driven Security Operations and Incident Response Capabilities	Journal	Germany	1	1	1	1	1	1	6.0
[Bitzer et al., 2023]	Managing the inevitable – a maturity model to establish incident response management capabilities	Journal	Germany	1	1	0.5	1	1	1	5.5
[Gomez et al., 2024]	Maturity Model of Response Protocols to Ransomware Scenarios in the Mining Sector	Conference Proceedings	Peru	1	1	1	1	1	1	6.0

The quality assessment was applied only to studies that met all inclusion criteria.

SM-D. Data Extraction Template

This section presents the complete data-extraction template used in the review.

The data extraction process was guided by the template defined in Table 4, which was specifically designed to systematically collect both descriptive and analytical information from the 6 selected primary studies. This template was explicitly developed to align with the research questions of the review, ensuring that all extracted data contributes to answering them.

By mapping the extracted data to these perspectives, the template enables a systematic, replicable, and comparable analysis of the selected IRM maturity models, supporting insights across all research questions while capturing both conceptual and practical dimensions of the models.

Table 4: Data extraction template for IRM maturity models (academic focus)

Item	Data	Description
Category 1 – Model Identification		
I1	Model name	Official name of the maturity, readiness, or capability model.
I2	Year created	Year when the maturity model was developed.
I3	Model type / lineage	Type of model and its derivation (e.g., maturity model, capability model, hybrid).
I4	Model purpose	Objective of the model, specifying aspects of incident response it aims to measure or improve.
I5	Validation method / empirical evidence	Methods used to validate the model, including case studies, expert review, simulations, or empirical evaluations.
Category 2 – Internal Structure		
I6	Leveling approach / model approach	Methodology used to structure maturity levels or capability progression.
I7	# of domains / # of areas / # of practices / # of maturity levels	Quantitative description of model structure.

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Item	Data	Description
I8	Names of domains	Labels of the main domains or dimensions.
I9	Names of areas	Labels of areas or subdimensions within each domain.
I10	Names of practices	Specific practices or activities defined in each area.
I11	Names of maturity levels	Labels for each maturity stage (e.g., Initial, Defined, Managed, Optimized).
Category 3 – Maturity Assessment		
I12	Assessment method	Approach to evaluate maturity (e.g., questionnaires, interviews, audits, simulations).
I13	Application method	How the assessment is conducted (self-assessment, external evaluation, software-assisted, hybrid).
I14	Evaluation criteria / basis	Rules or criteria used to score and interpret maturity (qualitative, quantitative, or hybrid).
I15	Numeric calculation / model output	Scoring mechanisms, weighting schemes, and forms of output (numeric score, maturity level, heatmap, radar chart).
Category 4 – Standards, Governance, and Compliance		
I16	Alignment with IRM framework	Extent to which the model aligns with recognized IRM frameworks (e.g., ISO/IEC 27035, NIST SP 800-61, CMMI) and how this informs capability coverage.
I17	Governance, policies, and compliance	Embedded governance structures, internal incident response policies, and adherence to regulations (e.g., GDPR, ISO 27001), ensuring conceptual and practical alignment.
Category 5 – Contextual Applicability		
I18	Scope (Specific / Generic)	Whether the model is designed for specific organizational types or broadly applicable.

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Item	Data	Description
I19	Field of application	Organizational or operational context in which the model has been applied.
I20	Adaptation sector	Industry or sector for which the model is tailored (if any).
I21	Incident management coverage	IR lifecycle phases or capabilities covered by the model (Preparation, Detection, Containment, Recovery, Lessons Learned).
I22	Mitigation strategies	Recommended actions or strategies for mitigating incidents.
I23	Cooperation / collaboration	Extent of internal and external collaboration supported by the model (teams, departments, CSIRTs, regulators).

By systematically completing the fields in the data extraction template, we ensured a comprehensive, replicable, and methodologically rigorous comparison of the selected incident response maturity models.

SM-E. Non-exhaustive list of representative industry-oriented IRM maturity and capability frameworks used for contextual comparison

Table 5: IRM dataset (Part 1/5): Bibliographic metadata.

ID	Article Title	Authors	Venue	Venue Name	Year
1	CREST (Cyber Security Incident Response Guide)	CREST	Industry / Professional Body	CREST	2014
2	Study on CSIRT Maturity: ENISA CSIRT Maturity Assessment Model	ENISA	Government / EU Agency	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA)	2019
3	What's your cyber readiness score?	Hiscox Group	Industry / Corporate Report	Hiscox Cyber Readiness Report	2022
4	Incident Response Maturity Assessment	Nettitude / LRQA Nettitude	Industry / Professional Service Offering	Nettitude (LRQA)	2021
5	Incident Response Maturity and the Roadmap to Success	Vectra AI Security Research team	Industry / Corporate Blog	Vectra AI	2020

Table 6: IRM dataset (Part 2/5): Model identity and approach.

ID	DOI/URL	Model Name	Model Type (Lineage)	Model Purpose	Validation Method / Leveling Approach
1	https://www.crest-approved.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/CSIR-Procurement-Guide-1.pdf	CREST Cyber Security Incident Response Guide	Process-based	Readiness	Industry adoption; practitioner review / Guideline-based (no maturity levels)
2	https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/enisa-csirt-maturity-framework	ENISA CSIRT Maturity Assessment Model	CMM-like, Capability-based	Maturity assessment	Expert-driven design; EU-wide CSIRT adoption / Staged
3	https://www.hiscoxgroup.com/cyber-maturity	Hiscox Cyber Readiness Maturity	Benchmarking-oriented, Risk-based	Readiness; benchmarking cyber preparedness	Large-scale survey (>5,000 companies) / Continuous / Score-based
4	https://www.nettitude.com/uk/incident-response/ir-maturity-assessment/	Nettitude Incident Response Maturity Assessment	Process-based, Capability-based	Readiness / Capability assessment	Professional service deployment and benchmarking / Staged
5	https://www.vectra.ai/blogpost/incident-response-maturity-and-the-roadmap-to-success	Vectra Incident Response Maturity Model (adapted from James Webb)	CMM-like, Process-based	Maturity conceptual assessment	Industry publication; advisory evolution / Staged

Table 7: IRM dataset (Part 3/5): Structure and assessment (simplified).

ID	Counts (D/A/P/L)	Names of domains	Name of practices	Maturity lev- els / Assessment method
1	~4 / ~3 / ~15-20 / Not explicitly defined	Preparation, De- tection, Response, Recovery	Incident handling, communication, esca- lation	Not explicitly defined / Checklist-based review
2	4 / ~8-10 / ~45 / 3	Organization, People, Tools, Processes	Incident handling, coordination, anal- ysis, information sharing	Basic, Intermediate, Advanced / Struct- ured self-assessment questionnaire
3	6 / ~3 / Not pub- lished exact counts / 3	Behavioral, People, Process, Technology	Survey-based items (not explicitly de- fined)	Novice / Intermedi- ate / Expert / Inter- active self-assessment tool
4	~3 / ~3 / ~10-15 / Not explicitly defined	People, Processes, Technology	IR policy review, readiness planning, log review, improve- ment recs	Not formally pub- lished / Consultant- led capability assess- ment
5	5 / 2 / 5 / 5	Incident Response Maturity (React-Ad Hoc to Predictive Defence)	Reactive; Tool- driven; Process- driven; Intelligence- driven; Predictive defence	Five conceptual stages / Qualita- tive assessment

Table 8: IRM dataset (Part 4/5): Application and outputs.

ID	Application Method	Evaluation Criteria Basis	Numeric Cal- culation	Model Output	Alignment with IRM Framework / Scope
1	Self-assessment / guided review	Best practices	None	Readiness check- list and guidance	NIST SP 800-61 Rev.2 – Com- puter Security Incident Han- dling Guide / Generic
2	Self-assessment supported by assessment tool	Capability cri- teria and SIM3 parameters	Qualitative to semi- quantitative scoring	Maturity profile per domain + overall CSIRT level	Based on SIM3; aligned with NIS/NIS2 IR requirements / Specific
3	Self-assessment through online survey	Industry sur- vey responses; best-practice benchmarks	Score aggregated into level cate- gories	Cyber readiness score (novice / intermediate / expert)	Partial align- ment with best- practice risk frameworks / Generic
4	Facilitated as- sessment by professional ser- vice provider	Benchmarking vs best practices + practical ob- servations	Implicit scoring / benchmarking (not public)	Capability re- port + gap anal- ysis + improve- ment roadmap	Partial align- ment with NIST CSF & IR life- cycle practices / Generic
5	Self-assessment / guided bench- marking (con- ceptual)	Conceptual cri- teria (threat awareness + re- sponse agility)	None	Conceptual ma- turity stages and guidance	Conceptual alignment with IR maturity frameworks / Generic

Table 9: IRM dataset (Part 5/5): Scope of use and IR coverage.

ID	Field of Application	Adaptation Sector	Incident Mgmt Coverage	Mitigation Strategies	Cooperation / Collaboration
1	Cybersecurity Incident Response	Cross-sector	Preparation, Detection, Response, Recovery	Operational mitigation embedded (containment/eradication/recovery), not standalone framework	Strong emphasis on internal coordination across technical, managerial, and support functions
2	Cybersecurity Incident Response (CSIRT operations)	Government / National / Sectoral CSIRTs	Preparation, Detection, Response, Recovery (organizational + coordination focus)	Explicit capability-level mitigation through CSIRT operational and coordination processes	Explicit internal and external collaboration via CSIRT coordination + information sharing
3	Cybersecurity preparedness / readiness	SMEs & Enterprises (business-focused)	Partial (overall preparedness; not full IR life-cycle)	Implicit (suggests improvements, not formal strategies)	Implicit internal and benchmark-based collaboration insights
4	Incident response capability evaluation and improvement	Cross-sector (consultancy-driven)	Partial (readiness + capability improvement focus)	Implicit improvements based on identified gaps	Internal coordination emphasis; external collaboration implicit through professional guidance
5	Incident Response capability evaluation	Cross-sector (consultancy-driven)	Partial (awareness + response agility; less recovery)	Implicit mitigation (awareness/agility improve mitigation)	Internal capabilities emphasis; external collaboration implied (threat intel integration)

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